

LRS BIANCHI TYPE-I COSMOLOGICAL MODEL WITH DARK ENERGY AND CONSTANT DECLARATION PARAMETER IN BRANS-DICKE THEORY OF GRAVITATION

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Abstract

Bianchi type-I dark energy cosmological model with variable equation of state (EoS) parameter in (Nordtvedt 1970) general scalar tensor theory of gravitation .To get a determinate solution of the field equation we take the help of special law of variation for Hubble parameter presented by Barman(1983) which yields a cosmological model with negative constant deceleration parameter. Some physical and kinematical properties of model are also discussed.

Key words: Dark energy, cosmological model, Bianchi type-I

1. Introduction

Einstein's theory of general relativity is one of the most beautiful structures of theoretical physics which describes the theory of gravitation in terms of geometry. It has provided a sophisticated theory of gravitation. It is based on the fundamental idea of relativity of all kinds of motion. The special theory of relativity formulated by Einstein (1905) makes a restricted use of this general idea since it merely assumes the relativity of uniform translator motion in a region of free space where gravitational effects can be neglected. As such it fails to study relative motion in accelerated frame of reference and is not applicable to all kinds of motion. Taking into account these limitations, Einstein (1916) generalized the special theory of relativity.

In recent years, there have been some interesting attempts to generalize the general theory of relativity by incorporating Mach's principle and other certain desired features which are lacking in the original theory. With this objective, various versions of scalar-tensor theories of gravitation have been suggested and widely discussed. Among these theories which are attracting more and more attention from physicists are the scalar-tensor theories proposed by Brans and Dicke (1961) [4], Nordtvedt (1970) [15], Saez and Ballester (1986) [30] etc.

Nordtvedt(1970) proposed a general class of scalar-tensor gravitational theories in which the parameter ω of the

Brans and Dicke theory is allowed to be an arbitrary (positive definite) function of the scalar field $(\omega \rightarrow \omega(\phi))$.

The field equations of general scalar-tensor theory proposed by Nordtvedt are

$$R_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} g_{ij} R = -8\pi\phi^{-1} T_{ij} - \omega\phi^{-2} \left(\phi_{,i}\phi_{,j} - \frac{1}{2} g_{ij}\phi_{,k}\phi^{,k} \right) - \phi^{-1} (\phi_{;i;j} - g_{ij} \square \phi) \quad (1)$$

$$\square \phi = \phi_{;i;k} = \frac{8\pi T}{3+2\omega} - \frac{1}{(3+2\omega)} \frac{d\omega}{d\phi} \phi_{,i}\phi^{,i} \quad (2)$$

where R_{ij} is the Ricci tensor, R is the Curvature invariant, T_{ij} is the stress energy of the matter, comma and semicolon denote partial and covariant differentiation respectively.

(We use gravitational units $8\pi G = C = 1$).

$$T^i_j = 0 \tag{3}$$

Also, we have

which is a consequence of the field equations (2) and (3).

Recently, there has been considerable interest in cosmological models with dark energy in general relativity because of the fact that our universe is currently undergoing an accelerated expansion which has been confirmed by a host of observations, such as type Ia supernovae (Reiss et al.1998 [29]; Perl mutter et al.1999 [17]; and Tegmark et al.2004[35]). Based on these observations, cosmologists have accepted the idea of dark energy, which is a fluid with negative presence making up around 70% of the present universe energy content to be responsible for this acceleration due to repulsive gravitation. Cosmologists have proposed many candidates for dark energy to fit the current observations such as cosmological constant, tachyon, quintessence, phantom and so on. Current studies to extract the properties of a dark energy component of the Universe from observational data focus on the determination of its equation of state $w(t)$, which is the ratio of the dark energy's pressure to its energy density

$w(t) = \frac{p}{\rho}$, which is not necessarily constant. The methods for restoration of the quantity $w(t)$ from expressional data have been developed (Sahni and Starobinsky 2006 [31]), and an analysis of the experimental data has been conducted to determine this parameter as a function of cosmological time (Sahni et al. 2008 [32]). Recently, the parameter $w(t)$ has been calculated with some reasoning which reduced to some simple parameterization of the dependences by some authors (Huterer and Turner 2001 [8]; Weller and Albrecht 2002 [38]; Linden and Virey 2008 [13]; Krauss et al. 2007 [10]; Usmani et al. 2008 [37]; Chen et al. 2009 [6]). The simplest dark energy candidate is the vacuum energy ($w = -1$), which is mathematically equivalent to the cosmological constant (Λ). The other conventional alternatives, which can be described by minimally coupled scalar fields, are quintessence ($w > -1$), phantom energy ($w < -1$) and quintom (that can across from phantom region to quintessence region as evolved) and have time dependent EoS parameter. Due to lack observational evidence in making a distinction between constant and variable w , usually the equation of state parameter is considered as a constant (Kujat et al.2002 [11]; Bartelmann et al.2005 [2]) with phase wise value $-1, 0,+1/3$ and $+1$ for vacuum fluid, dust fluid, radiation and stiff dominated universe, respectively. But in general, w is a function of time or redshift (Jimenez 2003 [9]; Das et al. 2005 [7]).

For instance, quintessence models involving scalar fields give rise to time dependent EoS parameter w (Turner and white 1997 [36]; Caldwell et al.1998 [5]; Steinhardt et al. 1999 [34]). Ray et al. (2010) [28], Yadav and Yadav (2010) [39], Kumar (2010) [12] and Pradhan et al. (2011) [16] are some of the authors who have investigated dark energy models in general relativity with variable EoS parameter in different contexts.

Bianchi type space-times play a vital role in understanding and description of the early stages of evolution of the universe. In particular, the study of Bianchi type - II, VIII & IX universes are important because familiar solutions like FRW universe with positive curvature, the de Sitter universe, the Taub- Nut solutions etc correspond of Bianchi type-II, VIII & IX space- times. Rao et al (2008a, 2008b, 2008c) [23]-[25], have studied Bianchi type - II, VIII & IX various cosmological models in different theories of gravitation. Rao et al. (2012) have studied Bianchi type- I dark energy model in Saez – Ballester (1986) [30] scalar tensor theory of gravitation. Naidu et al. (2012) [14] have obtained LRS Bianchi type – II dark energy model in a scalar tensor theory of gravitation. Rao and Sreedevi Kumari

(2012) [20] have discussed a cosmological model with negative constant deceleration parameter in a general scalar tensor theory of gravitation. Recently Rao et al. (2012) [18] have discussed LRS Bianchi type-I dark energy cosmological model in Brans-Dicke (1961) [4] theory of gravitation.

2. Metric and Field Equations

We consider the LRS Bianchi type-I metric in the form

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - A^2 dx^2 - B^2 (dy^2 + dz^2) \quad (4)$$

where A & B are functions of cosmic time 't' only.

The energy momentum tensor of the fluid can be written in diagonal form as

$$T_j^i = \text{diag}[T_0^0, T_1^1, T_2^2, T_3^3] \quad (5)$$

We can parameterize the components of the Energy Momentum tensor as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T_j^i &= \text{diag}[\rho, -p_x, -p_y, -p_z] \\ &= \text{diag}[1, -w_x, -w_y, -w_z] \rho \\ &= \text{diag}[1, -w, -(w + \gamma), -(w + \gamma)] \rho \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where ρ is the energy density of the fluid. p_x, p_y and p_z are the pressures, w_x, w_y and w_z are the

directional equation of state (EoS) parameters of the fluid along x, y and z axes respectively and $w(t) = \frac{p}{\rho}$ is the deviation free EoS parameter of the fluid. Here we have parameterized the deviation from isotropy by setting $w_x = w$. Also γ is the skewness parameter, which is deviation from w along y and z axes. The parameters w, γ are not necessarily constants and can be functions of the cosmic time 't'.

Using comoving coordinates, the field equations for the metric (4) with the help of (6) can be written as

$$2 \frac{\ddot{B}}{B} + \left(\frac{\dot{B}}{B} \right)^2 + \frac{\omega \left(\frac{\dot{\phi}}{\phi} \right)^2}{2} + \frac{\ddot{\phi}}{\phi} + 2 \frac{\dot{\phi}}{\phi} \left(\frac{\dot{B}}{B} \right) = -8\pi\phi^{-1} w \rho \quad (7)$$

$$\left(\frac{\ddot{A}}{A} \right) + \left(\frac{\ddot{B}}{B} \right) + \left(\frac{\dot{A}\dot{B}}{AB} \right) + \frac{\omega \left(\frac{\dot{\phi}}{\phi} \right)^2}{2} + \frac{\ddot{\phi}}{\phi} + \frac{\dot{\phi}}{\phi} \left(\frac{\dot{A}}{A} + \frac{\dot{B}}{B} \right) = -8\pi\phi^{-1} (w + \gamma) \rho \quad (8)$$

$$2\left(\frac{\dot{A}\dot{B}}{AB}\right) + \left(\frac{\dot{B}}{B}\right)^2 - \frac{\omega}{2}\left(\frac{\dot{\phi}}{\phi}\right)^2 + \frac{\dot{\phi}}{\phi}\left(\frac{\dot{A}}{A} + 2\frac{\dot{B}}{B}\right) = 8\pi\phi^{-1}\rho \quad (9)$$

$$(3 + 2\omega)\left[\ddot{\phi} + \dot{\phi}\left(\frac{\dot{A}}{A} + 2\frac{\dot{B}}{B}\right)\right] = 8\pi\rho(1 - 2\gamma - 3w) - \dot{\phi}^2 \frac{d\omega}{d\phi} \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{\rho} + \frac{\dot{A}}{A}(w+1)\rho + 2\frac{\dot{B}}{B}(w+1+\gamma)\rho = 0 \quad (11)$$

where the overhead dot (.) denotes derivative with respect to the cosmic time 't'.

Dark Energy Cosmological model in General Scalar Tensor theory of Gravitation:

The field equations (7) to (10) are four independent equations with seven unknowns $A, B, w, \omega, \phi, \rho, \gamma$. We solve these highly non-linear equations with the help of special law of variation of Hubble's parameter proposed by Bermann (1983) [3] which yields the constant deceleration parameter of the model of the universe.

We consider the constant deceleration parameter model defined by

$$q = -\frac{R\ddot{R}}{R^2} = \text{constant},$$

where $R = (AB^2)^{\frac{1}{3}}$ (12)

is the overall scale factor. Here the constant is taken as negative so that it represents an accelerating model of the universe.

From the equation (12), we get

$$R = (AB^2)^{\frac{1}{3}} = (k_1 t + k_2)^{\frac{1}{1+q}} \quad (13)$$

where $k_1 \neq 0$ and k_2 are constants of integration. This equation implies that the condition of expansion is $1+q > 0$.

Since the shear scalar σ is proportional to scalar expansion θ , we can take a linear relationship between the metric potentials A and B ,

$$\text{i.e., } A = \alpha B^n \quad (14)$$

where α and n are arbitrary constants and without loss of generality we can assign the value unity for α .

From (13) and (14), we get

$$A = (k_1 t + k_2)^{nk_3} \quad (15)$$

$$B = (k_1 t + k_2)^{k_3} \tag{16}$$

$$k_3 = \frac{3}{(n+2)(1+q)}, \quad n \neq -2, \quad 1+q \neq 0$$

where

Hence the metric (4) can be written as

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - (k_1 t + k_2)^{\frac{6n}{(n+2)(1+q)}} dx^2 - (k_1 t + k_2)^{\frac{6}{(n+2)(1+q)}} [dy^2 + dz^2]$$

(17)

Here we obtain LRS Bianchi type-I dark energy cosmological model in Nordtvedt's general scalar-tensor theory with

$$\omega(\phi) = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} \right) \phi, \tag{18}$$

where λ is an arbitrary constant.

From (10) and (18), we get

$$(k_1 t + k_2)^2 \ddot{\phi} + (k_1 t + k_2) k_4 \dot{\phi} = k_5 \tag{19}$$

$$\text{where } k_4 = (n+2)k_3 k_1 \text{ and } k_5 = \lambda[(n^2 + 2n + 3)k_3^2 k_1^2 - k_3 k_1^2 (n+2)]$$

From (19), we get

$$\phi = k_7 (k_1 t + k_2)^{\frac{q-2}{q-1}} + k_8 \log(k_1 t + k_2) + k_9, \quad q \neq 1 \tag{20}$$

where k_6, k_7 are the constants of integration and

$$k_8 = \frac{k_5(q+1)}{a^2(2-q)}, \quad k_9 = k_6 - \frac{k_5(q+1)^2}{a^2(2-q)^2}, \quad q \neq 2$$

3. Physical and Geometrical Properties:

The volume element of the cosmological model (17) is given by

$$V^3 = AB^2 = (k_1 t + k_2)^{\frac{3}{1+q}} \tag{21}$$

The scalar expansion θ for the model is

$$\theta = u^i_{;i} = \frac{3k_1}{(1+q)(k_1 t + k_2)} \tag{22}$$

The shear scalar σ^2 for the model is

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} \sigma^{ij} = \frac{7k_1^2}{2(1+q)^2(k_1t+k_2)} \quad (23)$$

The Hubble's parameter H for the model is

$$H = \frac{k_1}{(1+q)(k_1t+k_2)} \quad (24)$$

The energy density ρ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} 8\pi\rho = & \left(k_7(k_1t+k_2)^{\frac{q-2}{q+1}} + k_8 \log(k_1t+k_2) + k_9 \right) \left(\frac{9(2n+1)k_1^2}{(n+2)^2(1+q)^2(k_1t+k_2)^2} \right) \\ & + \left(k_7k_1 \frac{(q-2)}{(q+1)} (k_1t+k_2)^{\frac{-3}{1+q}} + \frac{k_8k_1}{k_1t+k_2} \right) \\ & \left(\frac{3k_1}{(1+q)(k_1t+k_2)} - \frac{1}{2\lambda} \left(k_7k_1 \frac{(q-2)}{(q+1)} (k_1t+k_2)^{\frac{-3}{1+q}} + \frac{k_8k_1}{(k_1t+k_2)} \right) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The EoS parameter w is given by

$$\begin{aligned} w = \frac{-1}{8\pi\rho} & \left[\left[k_7(k_1t+k_2)^{\frac{q-2}{q+1}} + k_8 \log(k_1t+k_2) + k_9 \right] \left[\frac{3k_3^2 k_1^2 - 2k_3k_1^2}{(k_1t+k_2)^2} \right] + \right. \\ & \left. \left[k_7k_1 \frac{(q-2)}{(q+1)} (k_1t+k_2)^{\frac{-3}{1+q}} + \frac{k_8k_1}{k_1t+k_2} \right] \right. \\ & \left. \left[\frac{2k_3k_1}{k_1t+k_2} + \frac{1}{2\lambda} \left(k_7k_1 \frac{(q-2)}{(q+1)} (k_1t+k_2)^{\frac{-3}{1+q}} + \frac{k_8k_1}{k_1t+k_2} \right) \right] \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \left[k_7 k_1^2 \left(\frac{-3(q-2)}{(1+q)^2} (k_1 t + k_2)^{\frac{-4-q}{1+q}} - \frac{k_8 k_1^2}{k_1 t + k_2} \right) \right] \quad (26)$$

The Skewness parameter γ is given by

$$\gamma = \frac{-1}{8\pi\rho} \left[\left(k_7 (k_1 t + k_2)^{\frac{q-2}{q+1}} + k_8 \log(k_1 t + k_2) + k_9 \right) \left(\frac{k_3^2 k_1^2 (n^2 + n - 2) + k_3 k_1^2 (1 + n)}{(k_1 t + k_2)^2} \right) \right. \\ \left. + \left(k_7 k_1 \left(\frac{q-2}{q+1} \right) (k_1 t + k_2)^{\frac{-3}{1+q}} + \frac{k_8 k_1}{k_1 t + k_2} \right) \left(\frac{(n-1) k_3 k_1}{k_1 t + k_2} \right) \right] \quad (27)$$

The cosmological model (17) together with (20), (25) to (27) represents LRS Bianchi type-I dark energy cosmological model with variable EoS parameter in a general scalar tensor theory of gravitation proposed by

$$\omega(\phi) = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} \right) \phi$$

Nordvedt with

It is observed that we cannot get explicit expression for the scalar field ϕ in this theory for the following two cases:

1) By taking the expression given by Barker (1978) [1] for ω ,

$$\omega = \frac{4 - 3\phi}{2\phi - 2}$$

i.e.

2) By taking the expression given by Schwinger (1970) [33] for ω ,

$$3 + 2\omega = \frac{1}{\lambda\phi}$$

i.e.

Dark Energy Cosmological model in General Relativity:

As $\omega \rightarrow \infty$ i.e. if $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ and with $k_7 = 0$, the present model reduced to dark energy cosmological model in General Relativity.

From (24) to (26), we get

$$\rho = \left(\frac{9(2n+1)k_1^2}{(n+2)^2(1+q)^2(k_1t+k_2)^2} \right) \quad (28)$$

$$w = \frac{-1}{\rho} \left(\frac{3k_3^2k_1^2 - 2k_3k_1^2}{(k_1t+k_2)^2} \right) \quad (29)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{-1}{\rho} \left(\frac{k_3^2k_1^2(n^2+n-2) + k_3k_1^2(1+n)}{(k_1t+k_2)^2} \right) \quad (30)$$

The metric (17) together with (28) to (30) represents LRS Bianchi type-I dark energy cosmological model with variable EoS parameter in general theory of gravitation.

4. Conclusions:

It is observed that the model has no singularity for $n > 0$. The spatial volume vanishes at $t = \frac{-k_2}{k_1}$, and it

increases with time 't'. Thus the derived model starts expanding with big bang from the point $t = \frac{-k_2}{k_1}$. The scalar expansion, the shear scalar, energy density, the skewness parameter, the EoS parameter diverges at

$t = \frac{-k_2}{k_1}$ while they become zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Also since $1+q > 0$, the model presented here represent an accelerating universe and also which is consistent with the recent observations of Supernovae Ia. It is observed that for $n=1$, the present model reduces to isotropic cosmological model.

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